

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ORIGIN OF CHILDREN WITH DIFFICULT UPBRINGINGS.

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Abstract: The article contains the content of the increase in the number of children with difficult upbringings, the negative aspects of their behavior from a psychological point of view, the role of social factors causing them to acquire a new color, and their consequences.

Key words: children with difficult upbringings, behavior, manifestations of behavior, reasons.

It is no secret to any of us that in recent years of social development, crime, drug addiction, prostitution, prostitution and suicide have become a global problem for countries around the world. Why, as time and social life develop and progress, the scale of these problems expands. Humanity seems to be opening the door to a number of challenges as the world evolves. When creating computers, telephones and morphine, not a single inventor thought that one day people would use their inventions for other purposes.

It is important to note that the number of children with learning difficulties has increased compared to ten or twenty years ago, and the number of causes and reasons is also expanding its scope. Naturally, due to the increasing scale of human needs and efforts to satisfy them, problems such as juvenile delinquency, drug addiction, prostitution, loss of mental balance, as well as such negative situations as loss of identity due to the influence of various social networks, are becoming increasingly common - increases every day.

In recent years, there has been a violation of standards for raising children of adolescence and adolescence, and a weakening of spiritual and moral qualities. This opinion was confirmed by school teaching staff and practitioners who spent three months of teaching practice in schools, and not only the parents themselves did not reject the fact that sometimes they themselves are powerless over the behavior of their children, based on analyzes and psychological and psychological studies. pedagogical observations. To be known. The scale of negative changes in children's behavior from a psychological point of view is increasing compared to fifteen to twenty years ago.

These conditions manifest themselves as negative behaviors in adolescents and young adults:

- Lack of education for adolescents and young people;
- spend a lot of time outside;
- rough treatment;
- increase in the number of suicide cases;
- prostitution;
- disability
- rapid irritability;
- disregard for the norms of decency and morality accepted in society;
- carrying bladed weapons;
- you use a telephone in an educational institution despite the ban and cannot imagine life without it;
- increase in the scale of alcoholism and drug addiction;
- rapid increase in crime (for example: robberies, hooliganism, even murders);
- acquaintance with various forms of mass culture; (clothing culture, external conditions)
- dependence on the computer and social networks; and zo.

Since the development of our society, the education of our children and at the same time the rise of society depend on their intellectual potential, why do such psychological changes occur in them? As an example, based on our observations and experience, the following factors can be cited:

Due to the emergence of psychological restructuring in women, that is, they achieve several social statuses (mother, woman, manager, worker), they do not have enough time to raise children, women have the opportunity to earn money, and they feel the need to get rid of dependence from a man. Usually, women's unemployment and difficulties in raising children restrain their desire to destroy the family. This does not necessarily mean that women should be housewives, but one cannot ignore the fact that raising children develops under the influence of mothers. That is, the question of how to raise a child if the mother is not at home, in our opinion, is reasonable;

Parents leave their children unattended for long periods of time for various purposes (work abroad, in different regions and for commercial purposes). It is known from the data that the majority of these children do not need education, create difficulties for teachers at school, and wander the streets in vain;

Addiction to computers and social networks. Obscene films and virtual games, which are the main interests of teenagers and young people, are the main factors in ensuring their addiction. Unfortunately, as a result of this, the norms of puberty are violated, the likelihood of leaving offspring is reduced, and virtual

games lead to the rooting of emotions such as aggression, a sense of addiction, and rudeness.

Negative aspects of using a phone include;

- This is an increase in the material needs of a person in society, as a result of which spiritual needs fade into the background. This, in turn, is reflected in the needs of adolescents and young adults. Feeling their needs met does not make them happy;
- inability to respond to social norms of adults who are a source of influence around the child;
- This is a mutual comparison of children's behavior and the emergence of negative psychological consciousness in children. In other words, it is emphasized that the source of the role model of parents is chosen incorrectly, but is chosen from relatives and peers, which does not always end positively, as emphasized in the article by M. Isakhanova "Negative psychological characteristics." comparison of children's behavior and educational capabilities."

In conclusion, it should be noted that as the era and time are updated, human socialization also moves on the basis of these changes. Thanks to this, the causes and characteristics of the development of children with difficult upbringings also develop. But it is not time that creates man, but man that creates time.

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